

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

Today we have sad news to share with you. We are deeply saddened by the passing of Arto Salomaa, one of the visionary founding members of our journal. Arto Salomaa, former professor of mathematics at the University of Turku, Finland, was a highly respected pioneer in the field of mathematical theory of computer science with a focus on formal languages and automata theory. Salomaa passed away peacefully on January 26 at the age of 90, surrounded by his family. Our thoughts are with his family, friends and all those who had the privilege of knowing him. His legacy will forever be a part of our journal.

It gives me great pleasure to announce the second regular issue of 2025. In this issue, 4 papers by 13 authors from 5 countries - Brazil, Germany, India, Pakistan and Turkiye - cover a great variety of topical aspects of computer science.

In a continuous effort to further strengthen our journal, I would like to expand the editorial board: If you are a tenured associate professor or above with a strong publication record, you are welcome to apply to join our editorial board. We are also interested in high-quality proposals for special issues on new topics and trends.

As always, I would like to thank all the authors for their sound research and the editorial board and guest reviewers for their extremely valuable review effort and suggestions for improvement. I also want to thank the readers for their interest in our articles, which is reflected in the increasing number of accesses and PDF downloads.

In the second regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce the following 4 accepted articles: Mehmet Ali Altuncu, Kaplan Kaplan, and Melih Kuncan from Turkiye discuss their comparative study of transfer learning models - Resnet-50, Resnet-101, VGG19, and InceptionResnetV2 - on skin cancer confirmation methods based on dermoscopic dataset images. Kiran K A and Jaison Jacob from India present their research on Energy-aware application mapping on 3D mesh-based network-on-chip using heuristic mapping algorithms where performance metrics such as communication cost, communication energy consumption, and CPU runtime were applied. In their study, Aneela Nargis, Muhammad Mobeen Movania, and Shama Siddiqui from Pakistan discuss an autoencoder-integrated WideResNet with dynamic optimization, which was designed specifically for the analysis of head and neck cancer gene expression data. In a joint research paper by researchers from Brazil and Germany, Ana Paula Allian, Frank Schnicke, Pablo Oliveira Antonino, Thomas Kuhn and Elisa Yumi Nakagawa look at the adoption of blockchain to trustworthy interoperability in Industry 4.0 systems and aim to highlight the challenges and close the gap between theoretical promises and practical applications.

Enjoy Reading!

Best wishes,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Christian Gütl', with a stylized flourish at the end.

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